

INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

Abdukadirova Matlyuba

University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences, Gavhar Str. 1, Tashkent 100149, Uzbekistan

Matlyubaabdukadirova412@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13253920>

Abstract: In this thesis, there are opinions about methodical approaches to teaching foreign languages and the role of innovative pedagogical technologies in it. Learning and teaching foreign languages has become the need of the hour in our country-Uzbekistan as well as in all developed and developing countries. It would not be wrong to say that the conditions created today for young people and all our compatriots for learning foreign languages are proving their positive results.

Key words: methodology, qualification, specialist, foreign language methodology, innovation, supply and demand, efficiency, debate and discussion.

1 INTRODUCTION

Among the reforms carried out in our country, attention is being paid to foreign languages, especially English. Not only in the case of foreign languages, but also in all areas of the world of science, serious changes and updates are being made on all fronts. Of course, at the beginning of such great creative work, the feelings of the honorable President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, attention to the youth, and confidence in the future are reflected.

Thanks to the large-scale reforms implemented in the education system in our country, incomparable opportunities and conditions have been created for the younger generation to acquire modern knowledge and grow up as a perfect person. In today's conditions, training of highly qualified personnel should be carried out on the basis of current systems and modern pedagogical technologies. Advanced and modern pedagogical technologies serve as a guaranteed tool for achieving the goal and show their positive results. In fact, 80% of the successful organization of each lesson depends on the correct development, organization and implementation of the educational process [3, 45-b].

Interent connection of foreign language and pedagogical technologies.

Today, learning a foreign language requires a spiritual-educational approach to organize each lesson on a unique, unrepeatable level based on the modern educational system and national heritage. The need to provide the educational process with modern pedagogical technologies is one of the conditions for the implementation of the "National Personnel Training Program". To provide young people studying in all educational institutions of our republic: pre-school educational institutions, general secondary schools,

vocational colleges, academic lyceums and higher educational institutions with modern pedagogical and information technologies, with a new knowledge system continuous organization of armaments is the demand of the times. The role of advanced technologies is very important for the student to express his opinion freely, to explain the topic in a group or team. Therefore, the goals and objectives of teaching a foreign language and its methodology should be in line with and meet the requirements of the interests of our society and the state, as well as the requirements of the growing young generation.

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. Naturally, learning the language of a foreign country brings many difficulties. However, in spite of them, today the youth of Uzbekistan are looking at foreign languages with great interest and passion. A question arises here. So, which foreign languages should the youth of the 21st century pay more attention to and for what purpose?

Time and foreign languages.

Undoubtedly, the development of the times, the process of globalization requires young people to know several foreign languages. The primary and main goal of the continuing education system is to prepare specialists with high morale, competitiveness and intellectual potential. Today, scientific and technical development requires the introduction of new modern technologies in every field, including the field of education. The demand for learning foreign languages has become a necessity at the same time, the demand for finding modern methods of language teaching and applying them to the educational process has increased. Today, the students of higher educational institutions

are directed to the process of education and training by doing practical work, not by memorizing the knowledge given to them[2, 79-b].

The educational process is a complex process. Today, every teacher should be able to effectively use pedagogical and information technologies in order to absorb new educational materials in the minds of young students, to strengthen the given topic, to help them remember.

With the development of the pragmatic approach in linguistics, in particular, in connection with the theory of speech acts, there has been an increased interest in the mechanisms of communication through language, its communicative function. Linguists focused on the language system and the processes of direct implementation of norms in practice. During communication, it became clear that a certain abstract norm or system is not implemented, but their options are presented by speakers, listeners, reading writers in everyday communication. Thus, the object of study became what is called speech in linguistics — any written or spoken text. It should be noted that speech is considered not by itself, but in the whole set of factors of its creation: who communicates, with whom, how and for what purpose. The main concept of linguistic pragmatics, and at the same time the methodology, has become a communicative situation, including all the listed and other factors that affect the nature, goals and methods of communication. This led to a real revolution in the methodology of language teaching, that is, it led to the development and formation of a communicative approach, the purpose of which is to teach communication in a foreign language, in terms of its qualities and characteristics, it is close to how its speakers use this language. Since all language operations are understood as an application of the pragmatic theory, the methodological system of the communicative approach considers the learning process as an action produced in language and language. It follows that this methodological concept involves the high activity of students and the loading of the maximum number of information channels as a necessary condition for successful memorization of language information and its subsequent use. The concept of communicative situation is considered by the methodology as a phenomenon that determines the logic of presenting material on the pages of the textbook and in the lesson. All exercises of the communicative approach in one way or another are related to the need to restore the real communication situation, master its parameters and develop the ability to transfer the learned material to all similar situations. Thus, there is increasing interest in various dialogue exercises, role-

playing communication situations, role-playing games, real communication simulations.

Methods used in modern training.

Innovative technologies are one of the factors that increase the effectiveness of education. For example, through methods such as "Brainstorming" and "Pinboard", we can see that the level of students and the interest in learning a foreign language is increasing. "Brainstorming" method is a method designed to test the knowledge levels of students. With this method, the teacher organizes a question-and-answer session to focus the students' attention on the subject of the lesson. In this process, the questions should be different, logical, interesting or related to the topic from a scientific and political point of view. This question-and-answer session can take 5-10 minutes, depending on the activity of students and young people. Using the "Brainstorming" method, students search for answers to various questions, use all possibilities to get out of problematic situations, and look for ways to get out of the situation. This leads to an increase in their interest in the lesson and a new topic, and their activation. When using this method, each student's answer is taken into account. The main thing is that each student is asked to justify and defend his answer.

In order to improve the effectiveness of the lesson, the most recommended method is the method known as "Pinboard". The word "Pinboard" is derived from English and means "pin-strengthening", "board-board". The main essence and purpose of this teaching method is that the discussion and educational conversation with the participation of students is directly connected with the practical method[1, 31-b].

A culture of communication and discussion is formed in every student. The ability to express one's opinion fluently and freely appears, logical thinking skills develop. The ability to express one's personal and worldly thoughts is formed when one goes to the blackboard or in front of many people. Skills such as being able to listen to one's peers, taking his opinion into account, sticking to one's own opinion, and proving another's wrong answer will appear.

Today, many modern technologies and methods are entering the education system. However, I think that how, at what time, and on what topic to use them depends on the teacher's ingenuity, inquisitiveness, organization of lessons and activities in a way that is both interesting and rich in scientific information.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Abdinazarov Sh. Actual issues of education, Karshi, 1991
- [2]. Khashimov O, Yakubov I. English language teaching methodology, Tashkent, 2003
- [3]. Jalolov, Jamal Jalolovich. Methodology of foreign language teaching: textbook for students of higher education institutions (faculties) of foreign languages / J.J. Jalolov. — Tashkent: Teacher, 2012. — 432 p.
- [4]. Zaripov F. Handbook of foreign language teaching methodology, Tashkent, 2002.
- [5]. Kadirova F. Pedagogical education, Tashkent, 2002
- [1] Dinara Saitkhanova (PhD) Understanding the role of digital technologies in education. (2024/issue03) “International multidisciplinary journal for research & development” Vol.11 page.128-130. journal India